

WORSHIPPING DIVINE STATUES IN ANCIENT ASSYRIA

*Protocol, Emotions, and Etiquette**

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1. Introduction

It is well known that Mesopotamian gods were worshipped in their temples in corporeal manifestations as living and anthropomorphic cult statues. This anthropomorphism was based on the notion that the gods shared certain features with human beings, such as size, age, gender and even in some cases mortality. The statue was the living embodiment of the deity and, accordingly, texts often refer to it as the god rather than as statue of the god. Mesopotamian statues were essentially a “work of human hands”, to paraphrase the prophet Jeremiah.¹ They were made of stones or crafted from wooden or bitumen core, plated with gold and silver, and clothed in robes with gold and silver spangles.² They were thus something other than useless, inanimate objects. To transform the humanly manufactured statue into a living deity and to assimilate the finite, physical image with the transcendent, intangible god, two rituals worked in tandem in ancient Mesopotamia. One was called “mouth-opening” (*pīt pī*) and the other designated “mouth-washing” (*mīs pī*). The former aimed at enlivening and sensitizing the god, enabling it to eat food and smell incense. The second had the purpose of achieving total purity and permitting the god to assume his position in the company of the other gods. The tablets which record these rituals originate from various sites

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¹ “I will pronounce my sentence against them for all their wickedness in forsaking me, in burning incense to other gods, in bowing down to the works of their hands” (Jeremiah 1:16; United States Conference of Catholic Bishops Bible). This is essentially the background of the theological issues and conflicts which emerged between iconodule and iconoclast and which characterized especially the monotheistic religions, Judaism, Christianity, and Islam. Investigations carried out diachronically on this topic have been collected in M.B. Dick (ed.), *Born in Heaven, Made on Earth. The Making of the Cult Image in the Ancient Near East* (Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 1999). On the ritual annulment of the human action, see Ceravolo, in this volume.

² Concerning the Neo-Assyrian period, see the following letters sent to the king Esarhaddon or Assurbanipal: S.W. Cole - P. Machinist, *Letters from Priests to the Kings Esarhaddon and Assurbanipal* (State Archives of Assyria 13; Helsinki: Helsinki University Press, 1998), texts 51-53 (from now on abbreviated as SAA 13).

(Nineveh, Assur, Sippar, Uruk, Hama, Babylon, Nippur, Kalhu, and Huzirina) and periods (eight to second centuries BCE) and demonstrate the centrality and vital importance of these rituals in ancient Mesopotamia.³ It was therefore through these rites that a statue “born in heaven” but made on earth received life and became a living entity.⁴

The result of these rituals was the constitution of a living divine statue, in which the deity was the reality, not the statue.⁵ The understanding of this phenomenon is not an easy task, and scholars have traditionally made recourse to the analogy with Roman Catholic Theology and the practice of the “Eucharistic Presence” to explain the relationship between statue and deity.⁶ However, independently of the question whether the statue was proleptically a god prior to the *pī pī* and *mīs pī* rituals (as in the Eucharist) or whether the statue started out as material and then became a god, the final entity which ancient Mesopotamians worshipped was an actual living and sentient being, possessing both a pre-reflective and an introspective awareness of actions. In other words, the divine statue possessed agency.

Both archaeology and philology have helped scholars to understand the procedures concerning the making of the divine statue and the rituals surrounding it to turn it into a living entity.⁷ However, we must reflect further on specific questions that emphasize the interactions between living divine statues and worshippers. With particular reference to the Neo-Assyrian textual and archaeological evidence (10th-7th century BCE), which acts, gestures, and

³ C. Walker - M. Dick, *The Induction of the Cult Image in Ancient Mesopotamia. The Mesopotamian Mīs Pī Ritual* (State Archives of Assyria Literary Texts 1; Helsinki: The Neo-Assyrian Text Corpus Project, 2001), pp. 27-29.

⁴ The expression “born in heaven” refers to the Akkadian incantation often found in the *mīs pī* ritual, which emphasizes the intense theological relationship between heaven and earth reflected in the making of the divine statue. In this respect, see E. Leichty, *The Royal Inscriptions of Esarhaddon, King of Assyria (680-669 BC), Part 2* [The Royal Inscriptions of the Neo-Assyrian Period 4; Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 2011], text 48: r 66-72.

⁵ I.J. Winter, “‘Idols of the King’: Royal Images as Recipients of Ritual Action in Ancient Mesopotamia,” *Journal of Ritual Studies* 6(1) (1992), pp. 17, 35 appropriately describes the rituals performed to make a statue alive as “rites of constitution”, because they bring the image, including the statue, into “being” through its animation and provide the context in which the Mesopotamian image or statue exists and functions. Since they are the very manifestation within the material form, these rituals are constitutive.

⁶ For the most exhaustive works in this respect and related earlier bibliography, see Walker - Dick, *The Induction of the Cult Image*, pp. 6-7; M.B. Dick, “The Mesopotamian Cult Statue: A Sacramental Encounter with Divinity,” in N.H. Walls (ed.), *Cult Image and Divine Representation in the Ancient Near East* (Boston: American Schools of Oriental Research, 2005), pp. 43-67.

⁷ On the making of statues in the Neo-Assyrian period, see D. Nadali - L. Verderame, “Neo-Assyrian Statues of Gods and Kings in Context,” *Altorientalische Forschungen* 46(2) (2019), pp. 234-248; see also, M. Ceravolo - F. Pacelli, “La creazione della statua di culto come atto religioso, politico e ideologico: il caso di Esarhaddon (680-669 A.C.),” *Quaderni di Vicino Oriente* 17 (2021), pp. 157-162. For the main publication of the *mīs pī* ritual, see Walker - Dick, *The Induction of the Cult Image*. For further comments, see C. Walker - M.B. Dick, “The Induction of the Cult Image in Ancient Mesopotamia: The Mesopotamian *mīs pī* Ritual,” in M.B. Dick (ed.), *Born in Heaven, Made on Earth. The Making of the Cult Image in the Ancient Near East* (Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 1999), pp. 55-121.

manners were performed by human beings to worship the imperturbable and inanimate but “living” divine statue? Because of the statues’ lack of behavioral traits, could they be considered “agents” in a full sense? To answer these questions and better understand the ways in which statues were worshipped, it might be useful to describe briefly how, in practice, Mesopotamians attributed agency to the divine statue in order to turn it into a “social other”, to borrow an expression by Alfred Gell.⁸ In fact, we can glean from the *pīt pī* and *mīs pī* rituals that no reference is made to worshipping attitudes before the statue was made alive. This happened only when the statue became a living deity.⁹

2. *The Life of Statues*

Statues were commonly subject to activities which inevitably and necessarily imposed agency on them by making them patients. Divine statues, or more simply gods, were enmeshed in the structured routines of daily life and the well-established apparatus of solemn festivities. For instance, a fragmentary letter sent by the governor of Kalhu to Sargon II probably pertains to a festival involving gods, where it is said that gods, meaning divine statues, get up or rise (*itabbūni*) and take residence, as though they were the subject of the action.¹⁰ In this respect, the movements of gods represented one of the dominant ways by which divine statues were perceived as actual gods and the statues as living entities. Dick, in his comparative analysis of the theology of the cult image in ancient Mesopotamia and the Eucharist, points out that the ways through which both “divine bodies” were viewed and exhibited was mostly in procession, permitting communication between the divine agencies and the human domain (fig. 1).¹¹ Textual sources abound in this respect and very often they describe this common practice.¹² Statues

⁸ A. Gell, *Art and Agency. An Anthropological Theory* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1998), pp. 126-154. For a more detailed analysis on objects as having agency in ancient Mesopotamia and how formal properties of visual representation and perception generate agency, see M.H. Feldman, “Object Agency? Spatial Perspective, Social Relations, and the Stele of Hammurabi,” in S.R. Steadman - J.C. Ross (eds.), *Agency and Identity in the Ancient Near East. New Paths Forward* (London, Oakville: Equinox, 2010), pp. 148-165.

⁹ See, for instance, the Ninevite ritual text, lines 59-65 and the Sultantepe version STT 200, lines 78-84 (Walker - Dick, “The Induction of the Cult Image,” pp. 89, 100).

¹⁰ S. Parpola, *The Correspondence of Sargon II, Part I: Letters from Assyria and the West* (State Archives of Assyria 1, Helsinki: Helsinki University Press, 1987), text 113.

¹¹ Dick, “The Mesopotamian Cult Statue,” pp. 44-46.

¹² See, for instance, A. Livingstone, *Court Poetry and Literary Miscellanea* (State Archives of Assyria 3, Helsinki: Helsinki University Press, 1989), text 7: 10-12 (from now on abbreviated as SAA 3). Similarly, see also SAA 3 6 and F.S. Reynolds, *The Babylonian Correspondence of Esarhaddon and Letters to Assurbanipal and Sin-šarru-iškun from Northern and Central Babylonia* (State Archives of Assyria 18; Helsinki: Helsinki University Press, 2003), text 9: 5-8. A report (Reynolds, *The Babylonian Correspondence*, text 80: 8-10) refers to the movement of statues on the occasion of a festival, making it clear that similar movements or processions often took place during special festivities.

Figure 1. Relief of Tiglath-pileser III from the Southwest Palace at Kalhu (BM 118934, © The Trustees of the British Museum).

could even spend the whole day in movement and come back to their temple, or literally their house (Sumerian *é*, Akkadian *bītu*), in the evening.¹³ Divine statues were even carefully dressed before leaving the temple¹⁴ and, during the excursions from their cellas, they participated in several activities, such as treaty ceremonies,¹⁵ promenades in the garden, and hunting in the game park.¹⁶ Statues could be exhausted accordingly.¹⁷ In all these instances, stat-

¹³ SAA 13 130. See also SAA 13 189.

¹⁴ See, for example, S. Parpola, *Letters from Assyrian and Babylonian Scholars* (State Archives of Assyria 10; Helsinki: Helsinki University Press, 1993), text 253: r 2-r 7 (from now on abbreviated as SAA 10). For a recent analysis with earlier bibliography on divine statues and clothes in the Neo-Assyrian period, see K. Neumann, “Gods among Men: Fashioning the Divine Image in Assyria,” in M. Cifarelli - L. Gawlinski (eds.), *What Shall I Say of Clothes? Theoretical and Methodological Approaches to the Study of Dress in Antiquity* (Boston: Archaeological Institute of America, 2017), pp. 3-23.

¹⁵ SAA 13 32.

¹⁶ SAA 13 70, 78. These activities took place during the sacred marriage of Nabu and Tašmetu. For further comments, see SAA 13, pp. xv-xvi and B. Pongratz-Leisten, “The Social World of Assyrian State Rituals,” *KASKAL. Rivista di storia, ambienti e culture del Vicino Oriente Antico* 15 (2018), pp. 245-247.

¹⁷ J. Jeffers - J. Novotny, *The Royal Inscriptions of Ashurbanipal (668-631 BC), Aššur-etel-*

ues are never mentioned as such but as living things, or actual deities, who go out and come back to their houses.

Being alive, accidents were bound to happen during all these comings and goings, and risks could compromise their life. Texts from scholars and priests often report the king taking trips with statues, such as the one sent from Akkullanu, a scribe of the Assur temple at Assur, to the king Esarhaddon: “Yesterday, on the 3rd, Aššur and Mullissu went out in peace and re-entered (Ešarra) safely; all the gods who went out with Aššur took up their residence in peace. The king, my lord, can be happy. [May] Ašš[ur and Mullissu keep the king, my lord, alive] for a hundred years”.¹⁸ The penultimate sentence of this quotation, which refers to the happiness of the king, implies how the life of statues ratified the wealth of a country or kingdom.¹⁹ In this respect, the auspicious timing at which one moved the living statues was one means used to protect the gods. Priests made careful choices regarding the auspicious and inauspicious days in which gods could take up residence or could leave their residences. This can be observed from a letter of Marduk-šallim-ahhe, a scribe of the Assur temple, to Esarhaddon or Assurbanipal, where Iyyar and Sivan appear as favorable months for letting gods leave their houses.²⁰

The foregoing discussion helps us to understand the ways in which agency was attributed to divine statues in order to transform them into a living being: statues could leave their houses or temples and take part in a variety of activities, and they could be harmed and even die with the dire consequence that the deity could leave the statue and the country plunge into disaster.²¹ The divine statue was the passive entity that was subject to various human activities, which enabled it to appear as a sentient being. However, the Neo-Assyrian evidence also shows how the agency of Mesopotamian statues was derived not only from the social activities which they were passively subject to, but also from the actions that statues were able to produce in their worshippers. In the context of ancient Assyria these actions were encapsulated in specific norms concerning worshippers’ access to the temple and the performance of worshipping acts.

ilāni (630-627 BC), and *Sin-šarra-iškun* (626-612 BC), *Kings of Assyria, Part 2* [The Royal Inscriptions of the Neo-Assyrian Period 5/2; Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 2023], text 220: iii 18’. My thanks to Joshua Jeffers for pointing this reference out to me.

¹⁸ SAA 10 98: 6-16. See also SAA 13 48. See also Parpola, *The Correspondence of Sargon II*, text 110: 4-7 and text 111.

¹⁹ The strict relationship between cult statues/gods and the wealth of the country also explains why statues, especially during the Neo-Assyrian kings’ campaigns, were targeted as part of the booty and conquest of a foreign polity. The act of “god-napping” is a particularly widespread topic in Assyrian royal inscriptions and the importance of living statues for a country is demonstrated by the fact that the names of the gods were intentionally omitted because of the anxiety felt at the sacrilegious nature of “godnapping” and destroying cult statues (S. Zaia, “State-Sponsored Sacrilege: ‘Godnapping’ and Omission in Neo-Assyrian Inscriptions,” *Journal of Ancient Near Eastern History* 2(1) [2015], pp. 19-54).

²⁰ SAA 13 12. See also SAA 13, p. xvi, and texts 4 and 6.

²¹ For a more thorough discussion on the daily life of statues, see Verderame, in this volume.

3. Protocol and Etiquette

Nowadays, we often encounter online resources and books which provide certain rules of correct behavior for those entering a place of worship. Following the comparisons proposed by Dick on Mesopotamian statues and the Roman Catholic Theology of the Eucharist, etiquette for Catholic believers might serve as a good example. Entering a Catholic church means being in the presence of the Eucharist, which is conceived as the body and blood of Christ, the son of God. This implies that one's words and actions must be appropriate and should reflect a desire to honor that entity and the church itself as the house of God. For example, God's house must be respected by keeping furniture, seating, and flooring clean and free of scuff-marks, trash, and stains, and by bringing no food or drink. Entering the church may dictate removing the hats for men, wearing clean and modest clothing, keeping silence, turning off one's cell phone, greeting one another with a smile, and standing and sitting when directed. The act of praying may include bowing one's head and closing one's eyes.

All these rules are not randomly prescribed for believers but are strictly connected with the meaning behind the Eucharist, namely the living body of God's son, and the house of God, as the holy house of God. Therefore, stances, manners, and gestures become meaningfully reverential: kneeling stands for humility; closing one's eyes allows one to forget one's local surroundings to connect with another world; folding one's hands helps to maintain composure; standing up may mean giving praise; and opening the hands may indicate a gesture to receive blessings.²² Ancient Assyrian sources do not provide us with similar guidelines and protocols. However, some textual and archaeological evidence can offer food for thought and help modern scholars in reconstructing the protocol and etiquette which governed the worshipping of gods in their temples.

Before proceeding, this examination requires the clarification of a few points. 1) Sources mostly deal with a royal courtly context, where the king is the main actor. As a rule, the acts, prayers and hymns recorded were mostly spoken in a particular social context, implicitly or explicitly under the guidance and authority of the palace and the temple and their leaders, such as kings and priests. Thus, although it seems essential to our contemporary concepts of worship, worshipping acts were more than just communications of one's personal concerns; they were mostly conceived as institutional actions. 2) Texts may offer information on the worshipping acts performed a) within the temple and in front of the divine statue, or b) at the home of the suppliant or in a secluded outdoor area (e.g. *šulla* prayers, which are often

²² L.J. Williams, *Church Etiquette: A Handbook for Manners and Appropriate Behavior in Church* (Bloomington: AuthorHouse, 2009); <https://justdisciple.com/christian-prayer-etiquette/>; <https://classroom.synonym.com/what-is-church-etiquette-12078226.html>.

compared with the Hebrew psalms),²³ such as those at night in order to address the deities in their astral aspects. I will focus only on the first category of sources, where the divine statue was the concrete recipient of the worshipping acts. For this reason, most of the information gathered here comes from ritual and cultic texts on specific festivals and larger rituals (e.g. Šebat-Adar festival) rather than from prayers and hymns. 3) The suppliant and the ritual expert – meaning the priest (*šangû*), diviner (*bārû*), exorcist (*āšipu*), or cult-singers (*kalû*) – seem to have been the only people involved in the actual performance of the worshipping acts.²⁴ Some royal rituals may have included a public element; however, worshipping acts, prayers, and hymns were not spoken in a congregational setting but were performed individually and in an individualistic framework. 4) Although prayers consisted of words and actions, appeals could also be communicated without words through a votive statue placed in the deity's cella or by a presentation scene on a cylinder seal. In what follows, only the first type of worshipping will be analyzed.²⁵

3.1. *Entering the Temple*

It is only by understanding the actual meaning of divine statues, or by understanding what they *are* rather than what they *represent*, that we can in turn understand why protocols and measures were adopted to protect the life of deities on earth, and why worshipping acts were carefully regulated and prescribed.

Compared to a modern place of worship, entering the Assyrian temple was not as immediate as we might expect. From archaeological and textual sources divine statues and their houses were heavily protected through the temple's spatial layout, doors and locks. If we take into account the main temple remains located near the royal palace, access could be even curtailed by its placement within a citadel. The route towards the cellas was impeded by the presence of gates and open spaces, which obstructed access and reinforced a sense of secrecy.²⁶ To further limit access to the temple, the

²³ A. Lenzi, "Invoking the God: Interpreting Invocations in Mesopotamian Prayers and Biblical Laments of the Individual," *Journal of Biblical Literature* 129(2) (2010), pp. 303-315.

²⁴ A. Lenzi, *Secrecy and the Gods: Secret Knowledge in Ancient Mesopotamia and Biblical Israel* (State Archives of Assyria Studies 19; Helsinki: The Neo-Assyrian Text Corpus Project, 2008).

²⁵ For instance, we are informed on the arrangement of royal statues within temples, sometimes in front of or next to the divine statue (Nadali - Verderame, "Neo-Assyrian Statues," pp. 240-245). Such an arrangement clearly implied the permanent performance of etiquette rules and thus worship of deities, reinforcing the encounter between the (statue of the) god and the (statue of the) king. This entailed that royal statues participated in the physical encounter, including all the etiquette rules involved, between the divine statue and the person of the king.

²⁶ K. Neumann, "Reading the Temple of Nabu as a Coded Sensory Experience," *Iraq* 80 (2018), p. 189. On the position and spatial layout of some Assyrian temples, see G. Loud - C.B. Altman, *Khorsabad II. The Citadel and the Town* (Oriental Institute Publications 40; Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 1938), pp. 56-64; J.E. Reade, "The Ziggurat and Temples of

entrances were also equipped with wooden doors with either one or two leaves. Archaeological evidence shows that a door consisting of two leaves provided a means of closing the temples and the main cella.²⁷ A fragmentary letter sent by Urdu-Nabu, the priest of the Nabu temple at Kalhu, to the king Esarhaddon concerning the loss of the keys to several temple-locks confirms the fact that access to the temple, and thus to the living statues of gods, was strictly controlled.²⁸

In addition to this physical protection, it seems that access to the temple for worshipping the statues and performing sacrifices was carefully regulated and granted only upon request and after the king had dispatched notices about auspicious days and times.²⁹ The performance of rituals in front of statues seems to have been allowed after submitting a query to the god Šamaš, as we learn from a query on the cult of Marduk from the reign of Assurbanipal: “[Should Šamaš-šumu-ukin, son of Esarhad]don, king of [Assyria, within this year] seize the [han]d of the great lord [Marduk i]n the Inner City, and should he lead [Bel] to Babylon? Is it pleasing to your [great] divinity and to the great lord, Marduk?”³⁰

The temple and its statues were constantly kept protected by the performance of purifying rituals and intense cleaning activity. An illustration of this is offered by a letter by the priest of the Nabu temple Nergal-šarrani from Kalhu, concerning the measures taken against a fungus in the Nabu temple.³¹ Similar controls were performed on divine statues, such as the checking of the garments and jewelry of all of the gods, to maintain an image that preserved the divine presence on earth.³² The interior of the temple must have been extremely well-cleaned and glossy. Moreover, we find references to the responsibilities of the temple personnel towards the temple itself and the cleaning activities of the temple areas as well as the praying/worshipping space surrounding the statues. What we glean from these sources is that temple personnel were intent in keeping everything clean. The picture that emerges makes clear that the temple received extreme care with respect to

Nimrud,” *Iraq* 64 (2002), pp. 135-216; J.E. Reade, “The Ishtar Temple at Nineveh,” *Iraq* 67(1) (2005), pp. 347-390.

²⁷ With respect to the example of the Nabu temple at Dur-Šarrukin, see the descriptions and pictures in Loud - Altman, *Khorsabad II*, pp. 58-59, pl. 20. Textual information on locking mechanisms in a temple is found in an inscription of Sargon II with reference to the description of the temple of the Urartian god Haldi of Musasir (G. Frame, *The Royal Inscriptions of Sargon II, King of Assyria (721-705 BC)* [The Royal Inscriptions of the Neo-Assyrian Period 2; University Park: Eisenbrauns, 2021], text 65: 372-376).

²⁸ SAA 13 62. See also S. Parpola, *Assyrian Royal Rituals and Cultic Texts* (State Archives of Assyria 20; Winona Lake: The Neo-Assyrian Text Corpus Project, 2017), text 50: ii 8 (from now on abbreviated as SAA 20).

²⁹ SAA 13 60: 16-r 8.

³⁰ I. Starr, *Queries to the Sungod. Divination and Politics in Sargonid Assyria* (State Archives of Assyria 4; Helsinki: Helsinki University Press), text 262: 2-6 (from now on abbreviated as SAA 4).

³¹ SAA 13 71.

³² SAA 20 50: ii 9.

cleanliness, as we can see in the list of priestly duties in the example of the Assur temple:

To sweep the area from the feet of the dais to the bottom of the House, to guard the utensils of the House, to remove the utensils, and to illuminate the pipes is the responsibility of the warden of the House. To sweep the area from the Kunuš-kadru gate to the threshold, to guard the gods of the *šahūru* ante-room, to fill the purification cones, and to guar[d] the golden thunderbirds is the responsibility of the warden of the *šahūru* anteroom.³³

Purification and cleansing rites were obviously imposed on those entering the temple accordingly. Purification was already required during the performance of the *pīt pī* and *mīs pī* rituals, where everything had to be well purified,³⁴ and the king was constantly informed on these activities.³⁵ Thus, we can imagine that, in order to enter the temple, purifying and cleansing activities were duly prescribed. In this respect, texts often refer to the importance of being pure (adj. *ellu*, verb *elēlu*) and clean (adj. *ebbu*, verb *ebēbu*) in approaching the divine: two terms that may imply physical cleanliness and/or may refer to purification from dangerous influence of curses, witchcraft and transgressions, as well as from culpability, metaphysical threats or sacrificial defilement.³⁶ For example, this is clearly stated in an hemerological text that contains proposals for action to be taken by the king before presenting himself in front of the statue of Šamaš, because of the omens reported: [In Nisan, the first day, he should cleanse and] purify himself. You soak [*zagindurū* stone in] filtered oil, [you put *maštakal* plant in]to [beer and oil]. He rubs himself repeatedly. [(...) he should put on linen] sandals and dress [in a new garment].³⁷ Similarly, the importance of being cleaned is often highlighted in the queries to Šamaš: “Disregard the (formulation) of the prayer for today’s case, be it good, be it faulty, (and that) a clean or an unclean pers[on has touched the sacrificial sheep]”.³⁸ It goes without saying that the hygiene and cleanliness of the body had to be matched by the cleanliness of garments, as we read in the *Assurbanipal’s Hymn to Ištar of Nineveh* which describes the encounter between the goddess who comes out from her temple and the king: “The king is clothed in clean garments, has put on a magnificent robe. Assurbanipal enters amid holy, pure offerings”.³⁹

³³ SAA 20 50: ii 14-ii 25. See also SAA 20 11: 18-20.

³⁴ Walker - Dick, “The Mesopotamian *mīs pī* Ritual,” p. 100, lines 74-84.

³⁵ SAA 10 247.

³⁶ This is not the context to discuss extensively the notion of purity, but it seems that terms for purity might originate from and could be related to a concrete sense pertaining radiance, brilliance, brightness, and thus purity of metals, such as gold and silver (Y. Feder, “The Semantics of Purity in the Ancient Near East: Lexical Meaning as a Projection of Embodied Experience,” *Journal of Ancient Near Eastern Religions* 14 [2014], pp. 87-113).

³⁷ H. Hunger, *Astrological Reports to Assyrian Kings* (State Archives of Assyria 8, Helsinki: Helsinki University Press, 1992), text 38: 1-4.

³⁸ SAA 4 5: 12.

³⁹ SAA 3 7: 13-15.

3.2. Approaching the Divine Statue: Emotional Impact and Etiquette

According to both written and visual sources, once the worshipper was duly cleansed and purified, any suppliant had to undergo tight customary procedures to enjoy the benefits of a divine meeting and which were carefully set up by the Assyrian temple administration. This interaction between the suppliant and the statue, since it took place in front of the gods and in a well-protected space, was framed by the set of rules regulating the meeting and, implicitly, by the accessibility to the deity. This appears clear in the priestly text quoted below, in which the temple official asks the king to solve the dilemma of his ceremonial and triumphal encounter with the statue of Ištar. Although the text does not describe the act of entering a temple, it gives an idea of the protocol governing the meeting with the divine:

Tomorrow Šatru-Ištar will arrive early from Milqia and enter before the king, and afterward the king will enter. Or the king will enter (first), and afterward Ištar will enter. As to which is acceptable to the king, my lord, the king, my lord, should write, and it will be carried out accordingly. Perhaps Ištar (will come) from there and the king from here (simultaneously). How will the king, my lord, fall under the gaze of Ištar? It is about this matter that I have written to the king, my lord.⁴⁰

This text is an interesting example of etiquette, in which the rules set for the interactions between the suppliant and the statue may have been established on a specific occasion. Curiously, it also alludes to the origin of the etiquette as potentially emotional in essence, especially when one considers the question that the writer asks to the king: “How will the king, my lord, fall under the gaze of Ištar?” (*akê šarru bēlī ina libbi ēnāti ša Issar imaqqut*). The verb used here is *maqātu*, whose primary meaning is “to fall down”, “to fall to the ground”, “to throw oneself down”.⁴¹ However, it can also be understood as a gesture of greeting and homage, on the basis of one attestation in a Neo-Assyrian ritual,⁴² and may additionally have the meaning “to arrive”.⁴³ Considering the subject-matter of the letter – who comes first and who later – the most appropriate understanding of the verb would be “to arrive”, as in the following literal translation: “How will the king, my lord, arrive before Ištar?”⁴⁴ Nevertheless, since the act of falling down to the ground was a very common greeting homage addressed to deities (see below), the translation proposed by the editors of the letter seems appropriate. In light of this reading, I suggest that the verb might be interpreted to mark the physical reaction

⁴⁰ SAA 13 149.

⁴¹ Chicago Assyrian Dictionary M/1 s.v. “*maqātu*”, pp. 240-242 (from now on abbreviated as CAD).

⁴² CAD M/1 s.v. “*maqātu*”, pp. 242-243.

⁴³ CAD M/1 s.v. “*maqātu*”, pp. 245-246.

⁴⁴ CAD M/1 s.v. “*maqātu*”, pp. 246.

of the king in front of the “eyes” (*ēnāti*) of Ištar. In other words, the gaze of Ištar forces the king to fall down, because implicitly no one can resist looking at her gaze.⁴⁵ In support of this suggestion, it might be worth mentioning a more explicit description of the physical consequences that the emotions exerted on one’s meeting with the divine as recounted in *The Underworld Vision of an Assyrian Prince*: “I looked at him and my bones shivered! His grimly luminescent splendour overwhelmed me, I kissed the feet of his great divinity and knelt down. Then I stood up, while he looked at me, shaking his head”.⁴⁶ In practical terms, the impossibility of looking directly at the luminescent splendor (*melammu*) and the eyes of the deity led the suppliant to fall down to the ground.⁴⁷ In spatial terms, looking is a form of access and looking at the statue’s face and divine splendor probably evoked emotions ranging from intimacy to audacity, and from sympathy to threat. This is perhaps why the approach to statues required suppliants to fall down to the ground first. It is the emotional impact with the divine that triggered the first act to be performed in front of a divine statue.⁴⁸

References to acts of prostration (*šukēnu*) abound in the textual evidence. One example reads: “On the 18th day the king goes down to the House of God. [...] [The king en]ters and prostrates himself in front of Aššur”.⁴⁹ The king Esarhaddon is said to have “kneeled reverently/fearfully” (*palhiš*) in order to seek the judgment of the gods Šamaš and Adad.⁵⁰ The same etiquette is carefully and constantly described in any episode which recounts the king or a suppliant approaching the statue. During the Middle Assyrian royal coronation ritual, we read that the king prostrates and his prostrating action is intensified by the expression of humility by rolling on the ground (*garāru*): [Having r]eached the Anzû gate, the king [en]ters the House of God. He prostrates himself and rol[ls] (on the ground)”.⁵¹ The prostration act could

⁴⁵ It is not by chance that in other representations of encounter between the Assyrian king and deities (e.g. J. Börker-Klähn, *Alt Vorderasiatische Bildstelen und vergleichbare Felsrelief* [Mainz am Rhein: Philipp von Zabern, 1982], pls. 188, 207-10), the king does not look directly into the eyes of gods and goddesses.

⁴⁶ SAA 3 32: r 14.

⁴⁷ The divine aura, or *melammu*, was a kind of radiant and terrible aura said to emanate from deities, as from temples, weapons and other selected artefacts. In this regard, see especially I.J. Winter, “Radiance as an Aesthetic Value in the Art of Mesopotamia (With some Indian Parallels),” in B.N. Saraswati - S.C. Malik - M. Khanna (eds.), *Art: The Integral Vision, A Volume of Essays in Felicitation of Kapila Vatsyayan* (New Delhi: D.K. Printworld, 1994), pp. 123-132.

⁴⁸ In this regard, see how postures of fear and adoration can be similar in iconographic representations (B.A. Strawn, “The Iconography of Fear: Yir’at Yhwh (יראת יהוה) in Artistic Perspective,” in I.J. de Hulster - J.M. LeMon (eds.), *Image, Text, Exegesis: Iconographic Interpretation and the Hebrew Bible* [New York: Bloomsbury, 2014], pp. 91-134).

⁴⁹ SAA 20 1: 1, 5. For the verb, see CAD Š/3 s.v. “*šukēnu*”, pp. 214-215; see also SAA 20, p. LXXXI.

⁵⁰ Leichty, *The Royal Inscriptions of Esarhaddon*, text 48: r 72b.

⁵¹ SAA 20 7: i 30-i 31. Interestingly, at the end of the coronation rites, magnates and royal eunuchs reciprocated the humble act by prostrating and rolling on the ground in front of the king (SAA 20 7: r iii 13). For the verb, see CAD G s.v. “*garāru*”, pp. 47-48.

be followed by the kissing of the ground (*kaqquru našāqu*), which implied falling on the ground even if not this is explicitly mentioned: “[On the 18th day] the king came do[w]n to the House of God. He k[is]sed [the ground] before Aššur”.⁵² Iconographic representations adhere precisely to this rule. For example, the altar installed by the Middle Assyrian king Tukulti-Ninurta I (1243-1207 BCE) in the Ištar Temple at Assur featured an image which shows the king twice, standing and kneeling, in front of an altar (fig. 2).⁵³

Figure 2. The altar of Tukulti-Ninurta I from Assur (VA 08146, © Vorderasiatisches Museum Berlin).

Beyond the act of prostration, it is plausible that the suppliant approaching the statue greeted the god with the raising of both hands or with the so-called *karābu* gesture, which the standard lexicons gloss as “to greet, pray, bless, praise”.⁵⁴ With particular reference to Neo-Assyrian visual evidence,

⁵² SAA 20 9: i 11-i 12. The act of kissing the ground is also a common and widespread act in Assyrian royal inscriptions (e.g. A.K. Grayson - J. Novotny, *The Royal Inscriptions of Sennacherib, King of Assyria (704-681 BC), Part 2* [The Royal Inscriptions of the Neo-Assyrian Period 3/2; Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 2014], text 163: r 4) and in the royal correspondence (e.g. M. Dietrich, *The Babylonian Correspondence of Sargon and Sennacherib* [State Archives of Assyria 17; Helsinki: Helsinki University Press, 2003], text 146: 10). However, it appears more often in relation with the king rather than with gods, especially when concerning royal inscriptions.

⁵³ For an examination of the altar, see Z. Bahrani, *The Graven Image: Representation in Babylonia and Assyria* (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2003), pp. 185-201.

⁵⁴ CAD K s.v. “*karābu*”, pp. 192-198. In this regard, see J.K. Chosky, “In Reverence for Deities and Submission to Kings: A Few Gestures in Ancient Near Eastern Societies,” *Iranica Antiqua* xxxvii (2002), p. 20; A. Zgoll, “Audienz – Ein Modell zum Verständnis mesopotamischer Handerhebungsrituale. Mit einer Deutung der Novelle vom Armen Mann von Nippur,”

scholars have proposed that the gestures of gods towards kings and kings towards their subordinates may be characterized by this verb and implied the raising of the hand.⁵⁵ However, on the basis of ritual and cultic texts from the Neo-Assyrian period, it seems that the main action performed by suppliants after entering the temple was prostration.

Finally, the other relevant actions that probably followed the prostration included the ritual action performed by the suppliant which – according to the Šebat-Adar festivals and various incantation-prayers – comprised purification rites, funerary offerings, food offerings and libations.⁵⁶

3.3. *In front of the Statue*

In analogy with human society, scholars have pointed out that the basic structure and rationale of a meeting with the divine involves the concept of an “audience”, in which someone presents a request to someone of a higher status.⁵⁷ The above-described introductory acts were essential: by the offering of a proper formal greeting in the form of gestures and gifts, the suppliant could then establish a reciprocal relationship with the divine, obtaining favorable recognition and reception. Only after following this specific etiquette could the suppliant then start to pronounce the words and perform the gestures that were required to worship the divine statue properly.

Texts and images preserve prayers and hymns addressed to gods as both verbal utterances and embodied acts, sometimes including kinesthetic or physically learned aspects.

As for verbal acts, we can see from the textual evidence that two different verbal actions could take place in such a ritualistic context: the uttering of a prayer and the uttering of a hymn, where the aim of the former was to seek assistance by communicating one’s concerns and petitions, and the aim of the latter was to bestow honor, praise and adoration upon a deity by enumerat-

Baghdader Mitteilungen 34 (2003), pp. 181-200; C.G. Frechette, *Mesopotamian Ritual-prayers of “Hand-lifting” (Akkadian Šuillas). An Investigation of Function in Light of the Idiomatic Meaning of the Rubric* (Alter Orient und Altes Testament 379; Münster: Ugarit-Verlag, 2012).

⁵⁵ U. Magen, *Assyrische Königsdarstellungen, Aspekte der Herrschaft: Eine Typologie* (Baghdader Forschungen 9; Mainz am Rhein: P. von Zabern, 1986), p. 39. See also Frechette, *Mesopotamian Ritual-prayers*, pp. 33-38; L. Portuese, *Life at Court: Ideology and Audience in the Late Assyrian Palace* (marru 11; Münster: Zaphon, 2020), pp. 115-116.

⁵⁶ SAA 20 1-6. For a summary of ritual actions performed during the reciting of incantation-prayers, see A. Lenzi, “The Language of Akkadian Prayers *Ludlul Bēl Nēmeqi* and its Significance within and beyond Mesopotamia,” in R. Rollinger - E. van Dongen (eds.), *Mesopotamia in the Ancient World: Impact, Continuities, Parallels. Proceedings of the Seventh Symposium of the Melammu Project Held in Obergurgl, Austria, November 4–8, 2013* (Melammu Symposia 7; Münster: Ugarit-Verlag, 2015), p. 84.

⁵⁷ W. Mayer, *Untersuchungen zur Formensprache der babylonischen “Gebetsbeschwörungen”* (Studia Pohl Series Maior 5; Rome: Biblical Institute Press, 1976), pp. 124-126; Zgoll, “Audienz-Ein Modell,” pp. 181-199; Lenzi, “Invoking the God,” pp. 308-309; Frechette, *Mesopotamian Ritual-prayers*, pp. 28-88.

ing its character and actions.⁵⁸ In this connection, it must be pointed out that Akkadian prayers may contain hymns, while hymns may lack prayers. The spoken prayer or hymn is often found in stand-alone texts, but it may also be embedded in royal inscriptions and diviners' queries or integrated into a complex ritual. As a result, texts have been classified on the basis of ancient scribal labels and rubrics (e.g. *šulla*, *ikribus*, and *tamitus*) or modern conventions (e.g. incantation-prayers, royal prayers, and letter-prayers).⁵⁹ This is not the place to discuss the etiquette prescribed for each prayer, but they have frequently associated ritual instructions so some important general elements can be listed in order to reconstruct the verbal protocol followed by supplicants standing in front of the supplicated (deity). If the written prayer was recited as such, then the suppliant normally begun with 1) an invocation of the deity by name, which aimed at catching the attention of the deity. This could contain 2) a hymnic introduction or praise, which served as a formal greeting, expressed through a list of divine epithets, attributes, actions and other features. Then, the suppliant identified himself or herself by 3) presenting his or her name, filiation and perhaps personal gods. The suppliant thus proceeded 4) to voice his or her concerns in the form of complaints or laments. The suppliant then referred to 5) the various ritual actions that have been performed, were performed, or will have been performed, and 6) concluded with a praise.⁶⁰

Concerning the physical acts which accompanied or preceded the prayer or hymn, these required the suppliant to adhere to a specific set of codes. For example, if a downward movement, i.e. prostration, characterized the beginning of the meeting, an upward movement ought to characterize the beginning of the "dialogue" of the suppliant with the statue.⁶¹ Indeed, it seems that verbs expressing "to lift" combined with one of several terms for "hand(s)"

⁵⁸ For an introduction to prayers and hymns together with a general discussion, see A. Lenzi, *Reading Akkadian Prayers and Hymns: An Introduction* (Ancient Near East Monographs 3; Atlanta: Society of Biblical Literature, 2011). The definition of prayer, in particular, may defy our modern sensibilities, although, to judge from the textual sources, a Mesopotamian prayer might be one which Alan Lenzi defines as "an appeal to some supra-human, benevolent being who is presumed to be powerful enough to assist in granting the appeal" (A. Lenzi, "Akkadian Prayers in Ancient Mesopotamia," *The Ancient Near East Today* IV (3) [2016]).

⁵⁹ Akkadian prayers are mostly known from first millennium copies found in libraries and collections in Assyrian and Babylonian cities, such as Nineveh, Assur, Kalhu, Sultantepe, Babylon, Ur, and Uruk. In this respect, see T. Abusch, "Prayers, Hymns, Incantations, and Curses: Mesopotamia," in S.I. Johnston (ed.), *Religions of the Ancient World: A Guide* (Cambridge: Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 2004), pp. 353-355; Lenzi, *Reading Akkadian*.

⁶⁰ Lenzi, *Reading Akkadian*, 12-13; A. Lenzi, "The Language of Akkadian Prayers," pp. 70-71. In this regard, as noted by Lenzi, the level of formality or informality used in prayers could be modified according to the formality or informality one used in normal social intercourse when speaking with people (A. Lenzi, "Narrating for Nabû: Power and Persuasion in an Assyrian Prayer to the Scribal God," *State Archive of Assyria Bulletin* 25 [2019], pp. 11-45).

⁶¹ This does not exclude the possibility that supplicants remained prostrated during the prayer (e.g. SAA 3 13: 19).

Figure 3. Golden seal of Hama, wife of Šalmaneser IV, from Kalhu, Northwest Palace, Tomb III, Bronze coffin 2 (IM115644; from T.L. Spurier, “Finding Hama: On the Identification of a Forgotten Queen Buried in the Nimrud Tombs,” *Journal of Near Eastern Studies* 76.1 [2017], fig. 6).

or “arm” preceded or accompanied the prayer.⁶² In general, these include the opening of hand(s) in supplication (*upnu petû*), perhaps cupped, and more often the lifting of the hands (*nīš qātī* and *šu ’illakku*), followed by the beginning of the prayer (fig. 3).⁶³ In this respect, it is also worth mentioning a text referring to the defeat of Teumman and the annexation of Elam, where we find the prayer recited by Assurbanipal: “When I heard [this piece of insolence], I opened my hands (in supplication) to [Ištar, the lady of Arbela]”.⁶⁴

Another example comes from the *Underworld Vision of an Assyrian Prince* and describes the prayer of Assurbanipal, which is most likely addressed to the underworld goddess, Ereškigal: “[*Once again*] he lifted his hands and prayed to Ereškigal, [his] tears flowing before Nergal, king of the [wide] underworld, her spouse”.⁶⁵ We are also informed about prayers that could be intensified to obtain a favor. In these circumstances, we can imagine that prayers could last

⁶² The raising of the hand(s) was probably conceived as a greeting gesture also (Zgoll, “Audienz-Ein Modell,” pp. 193, 196; Frechette, *Mesopotamian Ritual-prayers*). On the ambiguity of texts concerning the number of raised hands, see Frechette, *Mesopotamian Ritual-prayers*, pp. 42-53.

⁶³ It must be pointed out that verbs meaning “to pray” express the physical action performed by the suppliant. For instance, *nīš qātī* means “perform a hand-lifting” but it is an idiom for prayer; *šu ’illakku* means “of raised hands” but may stand synecdochally for a composite ritual activity performed within the *šulla* prayer. In other words, gesture and speech were closely related (Frechette, *Mesopotamian Ritual-prayers*, pp. 21-28).

⁶⁴ SAA 3 31: 14-16.

⁶⁵ SAA 3 32: 38.

days or months, as we read in the introduction to a query to Šamaš whether Assurbanipal should attend the holy places or not: “[Assurbanip]al, the crown prince o[f the Succession Palace, who for ma]ny [days], month after month, has day and night been moan[ing before your great divinity, O Šamaš]”.⁶⁶ Such an intense prayer could include additional gestures to convince the deity, being pronounced in a posture of supplication (*ina utnenni*) and with more humility (*labān appi*). We read of such a prayer in the so-called *The Sin of Sargon*, where the king Sennacherib is expending any effort to understand the sin which his father committed against the god. To do so, he collects the haruspices and the courtiers of his palace to enquire, by extispicy, Šamaš and Adad: “[In] my intense prayers and righteous[ness I daily spoke with my heart] [...] [.....] The haruspices whom [I had split] into [several groups un]animously [gave me a reliable answer in the affirmative]. [..... I opened my han]ds (in prayer) and lifted [my hands, and in supplication and humility I prayed on account of Sarg]on, [my] fat[her].”⁶⁷ The *labān appi* gesture (lit. “to stroke the nose”), in particular, has been visually associated by scholars with the gesture performed by Assyrian kings and queens on a number of monuments, in which the hand is placed directly in front of the face (fig. 4).⁶⁸

We are unfortunately less informed on the behavior imposed on worshippers during the reciting of prayers or hymns. However, some texts offer a glimpse of some rules that were potentially followed by worshippers to pray or praise a deity. Hints can be grasped from the dialogue between Assurbanipal and the god Nabu, where the god replies positively to the king’s incessant prayer by bestowing him with physical and mental strength to prolong his life:

[In the temple of the Queen of Ni]neveh I approach you, hero among the gods, his brothers; [you are the t]rust of Assurbanipal for ever and ever! [Ever since] I was [a small child] I have lain at the feet of Nabû; [do not abandon me] to the assembly of my ill-wishers, O Nabû!” *Pay a[ttent]ion*, Assurbanipal! I am Nabû. Until the end of time your feet shall not grow slack, your hands not tremble; your lips shall not become weary in praying to me; your tongue shall not falter on your lips, Because I will endow you with pleasant speech. I will lift your head and straighten your body in the House of Emašmaš.⁶⁹

Nabu’s response basically concerns the concession of a long life to Assurbanipal by dispelling from his life the human fate of old age (“until the end of time”) or illnesses. However, the passage may offer another reading of

⁶⁶ SAA 4 196: 1-3.

⁶⁷ SAA 3 33: 2, 21-24.

⁶⁸ The *labān appi* gesture was introduced in Assyria later, during the reign of Sennacherib, and scholars have variously interpreted it as a gesture of affection, praise, or entreaty of the gods. In this regard, see M.I. Gruber, “Akkadian *labān appi* in the Light of Art and Literature,” *Journal of Near Eastern Studies* 7.1 (1975), pp. 73-83; Magen, *Assyrische Königsdarstellungen*, pp. 105-106. See also Frechette, *Mesopotamian Ritual-prayers*, pp. 46-48 for a review of previous studies.

⁶⁹ SAA 3 13: 3-12.

Figure 4. Bronze relief fragment showing Naqi'a and her son king Esarhaddon (AO 20185, © RMN-Grand Palais [Musée du Louvre]).

itself. In one phrase, Nabu informs Assurbanipal that his lips will not become weary “in praying to me” (*ana mitahhurīya*). The verb used here is *maḥāru* and the sentence is translated as “your lips shall not become weary in praying to me”. The verb can have the meaning of praying to a deity, to pray to a deity again and again, but it can also be used to refer to a prayer.⁷⁰ In the context, the conditions that Nabu will dispel from Assurbanipal’s life are limits that impede anyone from praying correctly. What Nabu is thus proffering to Assurbanipal are the ideal conditions required for praying repeatedly to a deity and making his prayer pleasant, acceptable and accepted by a god.⁷¹ Therefore, with some caution, we may extrapolate from this passage the following rules which may have been part of the Assyrian praying etiquette:

the feet should not vacillate (*šēpu lā issanammā*)
 the hands should not tremble (*qātu lā inarruṭā*)
 the lips should not become weary (*šaptu lā ennahā*)
 the tongue should not falter (*lišānu lā tattaniggir*)
 the uttered speech should be pleasant (*dabābu ṭābu*)
 the head should be held high (*matāhu rēšu*); and
 the suppliant should keep an erect posture (*šatāhu lānu*).

⁷⁰ CAD M/1 s.v. “*maḥāru*”, pp. 61, 71.

⁷¹ In this regard, see also the following passage from the same text: “Nabū continues: ‘That pleasant mouth of yours which constantly prays to Urkittu’” (SAA 3 13: 13).

Visually, the last two recommendations may find iconographic correspondences in the suppliants which are carefully depicted with an erect posture and their heads held high (see figs. 2-4). To all these rules, I would add a further one which emphasizes the importance of uttering one's speech calmly in front of the statue and, especially, after recognizing one's own fault: "One who acknowledges no guilt rushes to his god, without thinking he quickly raises his hands (in prayer) to the god. ...his guilt... a man in ignorance rushes to his god".⁷² This teaching, which offers instruction about approaching a deity, points out the foolishness of rushing hastily to one's god without proper recognition of one's own state of mind. It was perhaps only by adhering to these rules that the suppliant could pronounce the prayer or hymn, and that these would be heard by the deity.

We are not informed on the gestures and acts that were performed at the end of the audience with a divine statue. However, we can only imagine that prostration and raising of the hand(s) were duly repeated by the suppliant who left the temple.⁷³

4. Conclusion

The foregoing discussion is not intended to be exhaustive or complete, considering the breadth of the topic investigated. Partly this is because such an analysis raises the basic question of where the boundaries between protocol/etiquette and ritual really lie, whether our understanding of one might help us to deepen our understanding of the other, and whether they ought to be regarded as part of the same family of practices. Nevertheless, while I hope to address these questions in the future, this brief analysis offers some general results.

First, what emerges from an examination of the textual evidence is that divine statues could be worshipped only when they were turned into living entities and assumed to possess agency. Consequently, notwithstanding their apparent inefficacy, statues converted into living beings were agents in a full sense by virtue of the fact that they exerted control on human actions, actions that were materialized in words and gestures. Furthermore, protocol and etiquette were not a formality at all in ancient Assyria: any mistake made during the meeting with the divine statue could compromise the relationship with the deity and lead to the loss of his or her protection, with ruin expected for the suppliant and the kingdom or family he or she belonged to. Finally, all these rules emphasized the importance of knowing the reasons why certain gestures were performed in certain ways. When the suppliant followed the

⁷² This is an Akkado-Hurrian bilingual text which comes from Ugarit and dates from the 14th century BCE. Although it is far from the period under investigation, its teaching is very general and perhaps valid for any time. For translation and comments, see W.G. Lambert, *Babylonian Wisdom Literature* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1967), p. 116.

⁷³ Zgoll, "Audienz-Ein Modell," pp. 196.

etiquette properly, he or she not only made certain gestures and behaved in certain ways, but also reflected on the reasons for doing so. These reasons constituted the very essence of the divine statue which was the actual deity, and the emotions linked to the encounter with the divine world. This means that the etiquette described in texts and especially represented on monuments is what enabled Assyrians to behave in appropriate ways according to the emotions felt at that specific moment when those actions were performed. In a nutshell, a knowledge of this etiquette marked a tangible acknowledgment of what the divine statue was able to trigger in human beings. By contrast, the improper performance of gestures and manners would have shown a lack of understanding of, and regard for, the divine statues, which entailed the risk of losing the divine beings' protection. Etiquette, in other words, was essential in regulating the relationships between human beings and the divine world, the latter of which was reified in the material divine statue.

ABSTRACT

This paper re-constructs the ways that divine statues were worshipped in ancient Assyria, by analyzing the protocols and etiquette that were adhered to by worshippers during their encounter with the divine. Textual and archaeological evidence does not offer exhaustive descriptions in this respect, but a polyphonic reading of these sources helps the modern scholar to explore the protocols that were followed and the gestures that were performed by the suppliant. It is concluded that the essence of divine statues, as well as the emotions experienced by the suppliant, produced those worshipping acts that today we may refer to as "etiquette".

KEYWORDS: Assyria, Statue, Protocol, Emotions, Etiquette